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Visual Astronomy Display: July 2014

Katie Frey

Updated on August 24, 2022

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Visual Astronomy Display for July 2014

Highlights...

- **Curiosity celebrates one Martian year** of exploring the red planet;
- Science@NASA shows that **the Sun is finally coming back to maximum** cycle after a long Solar minimum;
- **Transmitting videos from space via laser beams?** The goal of NASA's OPALs project is described in a video from JPL;
- Vincent Bradly's **360 degree night-sky time-lapse videos** combine daytime panoramas and long exposures of the stars for incredibly gorgeous effects; and
- The Hubble Space Telescope team reveals **the Ultra Deep Field 2014**, an image composed of 841 90-minute exposures from 2003 to 2012 captured in ultraviolet.

The History, and Future, of Space Suits

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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